

L. hexandra, *C. compressus*, *Cyperus rotundus*, and *C. iria* consistently harbored *P. oryzae*.

To study pathogenicity on rice, we inoculated potted seedlings of highly susceptible variety HR12 and popular variety KD2-6-3 at the 3- to 4-leaf stage with different isolates of *P. oryzae*. All isolates produced blast symptoms on HR12. The isolate from *C. compressus* failed to infect KD2-6-3 (see table). □

Diseases of deepwater rice in Jorhat District, Assam, India

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We surveyed 20 fields at different sites over some 6,000 ha of deepwater rice along the Brahmaputra River during rice flowering to ripening stages Oct-Dec 1987.

A general impression of disease incidence was obtained first, by walking across each sample field. A wooden quadrat 50 × 50 cm was placed at random along the field diagonal and the panicles infected with blast (BI) among those enclosed by a quadrat counted. Ten quadrat counts were made in each field. Other diseases were recorded similarly. For ufra, the top 30 cm portions of infested stems were collected to extract the stem nematode and to count nematodes per stem.

Ufra caused by *Ditylenchus angustus* was found at 15 sites. The disease appeared in distinct patches. On the average, 55% of the stems were infected in an ufra patch. The most common symptoms were nonemergence of panicles and half-emerged panicles.

In the most severe form of ufra, a rudimentary, skeletal panicle protruded from the boot (Fig. 1). The highest count of nematodes per stem was 7,500. Some ratoon tillers in ufra patches had chlorotic ufra symptoms: chlorosis of the youngest leaf at the neck region with brown stains on the midrib (Fig. 2). This symptom resembles a mite attack.

1. Most severe symptom of ufra — twisted ear protruding (arrow) from the boot. Assam, India, 1987.

Dominant deepwater varieties Amanabao and Rangabao were highly susceptible to ufra.

Neck BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* was the second most important disease. On the average, 25% of the panicles in 10 infested fields were infected. Ratoon tillers from basal stem nodes were infected with leaf BI; typical BI spots also were observed on the flag leaves. Nodal BI was common in several fields.

2. Chlorotic ufra symptom in ratoon tillers. Assam, India, 1987.

Amanabao and Rangabao were susceptible to neck BI.

Other diseases found were sheath rot (less than 1% stems infected), bacterial blight (5% leaf area infected), brown spot (less than 5% leaf area infected), false smut (1% panicles infected), and kernel smut (1% panicles infected). □

Host plants of ragged stunt virus (RSV)

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We inoculated young seedlings of 2 *Oryza* spp. and 15 weed species separately with 20 RSV-viruliferous brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* each. Inoculated plants were indexed by ELISA 30 d after inoculation. Extracts of plants with absorbance at 405 nm

higher than 3 times that of uninoculated plant extracts were considered to contain the virus.

Both rice accessions and six weed species were infected with RSV (see table). Infected *Oryza* plants showed typical RSV symptoms. Infected *Leersia hexandra* plants also showed symptoms. Weed species not infected with the virus were *Brachiaria distachya*, *B. mutica*, *Chloris barbata*, *Cyperus brevifolius*, *C. difformis*, *Eleusine indica*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*. □

Absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA of extracts of plants infected with RSV after inoculation by RSV-viruliferous BPH. IRR1.

Species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)	Absorbance at 405 nm	
			Infected plants	Uninoculated plants (mean)
<i>Oryza australiensis</i>				
Acc. 100882	14	2	0.13-0.48	0.00
Acc. 101397	12	6	0.07-0.29	0.00
<i>O. latifolia</i>	10	3	0.13-4.22	0.01
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	12	1	0.15	0.04
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	12	1	0.17	0.03
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	16	1	0.25	0.00
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i>	12	3	0.12-0.37	0.04
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	12	3	0.10-0.28	0.00
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	28	5	0.06-0.12	0.00

Differential transmission of tungro (RTV) by green leafhopper (GLH) selected on IR54

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We compared RTV transmission by a GLH *Nephotettix virescens* colony maintained since 1982 on resistant variety IR54 in the greenhouse and by a colony on TN1, using a selected set of 12 differential varieties. Seven-day-old seedlings in test tubes were inoculated separately at 1 insect/seedling for 24 h, using GLH adults that had fed on RTV-infected Pelita plants. Infection

symptoms (stunting and yellowing) were assessed visually 14 d after inoculation (DAI) and by latex serology 16 DAI.

Higher infection rates were obtained from the IR54 colony on IR28, IR29, IR34, IR50, IR54, IR58, and IR60, with resistances to GLH derived primarily from Gam Pai 30-12-15 (see figure). The latex test showed seedlings mostly were infected with both bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses. Inoculation with the TN1 colony resulted in infection mainly with RTBV alone.

Regardless of colony, IR26 and IR30 had high RTBV infection. IR36 and IR42 had high infection with both viruses.

These results indicate that GLH selected on IR54 have higher ability to transmit RTBV and RTSV on varieties with Gam Pai 30-12-15 in their parentage. Resistance of IR54 to RTV is conditioned only by its resistance to the GLH vector, not to the RTV-associated viruses. □

Infection (%)

RTV incidence based on symptoms and RTBV + RTSV incidence based on the latex test in rice varieties inoculated at 1 insect/seedling in test tubes by TN1 and IR54 GLH colonies that had fed on Cisadane plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV.

Combined ufra + blast (BI) infection in deepwater rice

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Ufra disease caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* is spreading rapidly in the deepwater rice